

Future Psychologist's Mental Orientation at the Correctional Support of the Children with Impaired Mental and Physical Development

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Abstract: *The practice of the integrated techniques of teaching children with impaired development of various nosological categories in comprehensive schools together with children with normal development is becoming increasingly extensive alongside with a series of researches in this direction. As it follows, in this complicated process a mentally correctional support of an educated specialist is essential for a child with impaired mental and physical development. The findings of the theoretical analysis of the role and place of the orientation phenomenon in the personality's professional activity have been given. Particular attention is focused upon the content, structure and formation levels of the personality's professional orientation in adolescence; as well as on the peculiarities of the correctional support in the context of the psychological assistance to the children with alternative abilities. The specificity of the empirical research of the peculiarities of future psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of alternatively able children has been described. The qualification characterization of a future special psychologist's support has been presented, the techniques and methods of the investigation of the psychological peculiarities of the professional orientation at correctional support have been outlined, the findings of the empirical research have been analyzed. The theoretical and methodological foundations of the psychological provision of the formation process of the future psychologist's professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with alternative abilities have been discussed. The organization of the activity aimed at the development of the future special psychologists' professional orientation has been described, methodological apparatus has been worked out and the approbation results have been adduced. On the basis of the findings the conclusion may be drawn that the suggested methodology is correct, the tasks have been successfully performed, the objective has been achieved, the efficiency of the methodological recommendations has been verified.*

Keywords: *integrated teaching techniques, nosological categories, mental correctional support, psychological assistance, adolescence, qualification characterization.*

How to cite: Afuzova, H., Rudenko, L., Stepanchenko, N., Shkrabiuk, V., Martsyniak-Dorosh, O., & Dubovyk, O. (2021). Future Psychologist's Mental Orientation at the Correctional Support of the Children with Impaired Mental and Physical Development. *BR-AIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 12(3), 127-148. <https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/12.3/224>

Introduction

In the focus of the national education development doctrine among the other directions of its further improvement there is constant increase in education quality, content and educational process upgrading, development of continuous education system and lifetime learning. The Ukrainian system of teaching and educating people with impaired mental and physical development is on the stage of evolution, defined as the transitional stage from the equal rights recognition to the equal opportunities provision, from institutionalization to integration. Due to the low social security of the population of Ukraine, the decrease in the quality of life level as well as the complicated ecological state, low level of health care the number of children with impaired mental and physical development is rapidly increasing. The main task of the modern science is to contribute to the full-fledged social adaptation of such children, their integration into the society by the introduction of the inclusive education system.

The practice of the integrated techniques of teaching children with impaired mental and physical development of various nosological categories in comprehensive schools together with children with normal development is becoming increasingly extensive and the researches in this field are more recurrent. As it follows, in this complicated process a mentally correctional support of an educated specialist is essential for a child with impaired mental and physical development. For a long time the psychological support of the people with impaired mental and physical development in the system of the special education was given in Ukraine by specialists without the proper professional background. It goes without saying that this influenced the quality and efficiency of the educational-correctional process. The system of special educational institutions and rehabilitation centers in Ukraine requires from the higher educational institutions the vocational training of well-qualified and competitive specialists for working with children with impaired mental and physical development.

While providing correctional support to the children with impaired mental and physical development there is distinctly actualized the stimulating function of professional orientation providing personal professional tenacity regardless the negative effect of the outer factors. The crucial role in training psychologists for working with the above-mentioned category of children is also distinguished. Orientation is the crucial component of the inner personality's mental structure, which to a certain extent predetermines all the person's actions and the ways of manifesting his/her other mental features and qualities. Orientation is interpreted as the

system of impulses determining both the selectiveness in the personality's attitudes to the environment and the objects this orientation is directed at.

The personality's professional orientation is revealed in his/her attitude to professional activity and presupposes understanding and inner acceptance of the objectives and tasks of this activity, expresses interests, ideals, settings, convictions, opinions which characterize it. At this stage needs, interests, values acquire entirely new sense in the personal development of a future professional.

The changes in the role and status of the specialists in the today's special psychology field is greatly dependent on the level of their professional orientation and competence. This, in its turn, explains the necessity of the professionals training system improvement in the special psychology field aimed at changing the level of their professional orientation, which will positively affect the quality of their professional activity of correctional support of the above-mentioned category of children in educational rehabilitation institutions. The choice of the topic of the research was determined by the task to reform education in the direction of humanitarization and humanization and the objective of the overall harmonious personality development, as well as by the need to improve the future psychologists training system due to the underdeveloped issue of the professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development.

The objective is to theoretically grounding and experimental research of the mental peculiarities of the future psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development.

Literature review

It has been concluded on the basis of the scientific literature review that the issue of orientation is viewed in modern psychology chiefly in the context of the two global scientific approaches: personal and active. From the point of view of the representatives of the personal approach (Asmolv, 1983; Palamarchuk et al., 2020 etc) orientation is interpreted as the system of relations, formed and evolving in the process of the person's social and mental development and reflected in the attitude to himself/herself, to other people, to the environment etc. These attitudes in the personality's orientation structure are in the hierarchic dependence according to the content-value parameter. Orientation is viewed as the basis of the personality, determining its social and mental characteristic, subduing to

itself all the forms of person's activity and favoring his/her self-regulation and self-realization. The supporters of the active approach treat orientation as the system of motives, determining the performance of some certain types of activity (Bozhovych, 1972; Leontyev, 1977; Sheremet et al., 2019). It's worth mentioning that the personal and active approaches are not mutually exclusive because they are often united in dealing with specific challenges. As it follows, the majority of scholars (Lomov, 1984; Nerubasska & Maksymchuk 2020; Nerubasska et al., 2020; Zeyer, 2006) distinguish in the orientation structure the personal component, containing needs, desires, interests, ideals, persuasions, world outlook, level of aspirations, self-esteem, human values) and the procedural component which lies in being active in one particular type of activity, necessity to acquire and enrich knowledge in particular field, need for self-cognition and self-development in a certain type of activity and positive attitude to it.

It follows from the stated above that the personality orientation is the main and multidimensional quality of the personality, uniting the inner mental conditions predetermining the person's social activity which is inseparable from the person's participation in social processes.

Professional orientation is viewed as the manifestation of the general personality's orientation. Personality's professional orientation has been investigated by many psychologists and educators in the last decades (Behas et al., 2019; Bezliudnyi et al., 2019; Iaremchuk, 1999; Potykha, 2000), nevertheless the complexity of the challenge is conditioned by the absence of the unanimous opinion about the understanding of the professional orientation essence.

From the psychological point of view, professional orientation is viewed as the leading, integral, socially conditioned feature of a personality and it mostly often is displayed as the selective positive attitude to the occupation (Seyeteshev, 1990; Slastyonin, 1976); particular kind of attitude: to the occupation, to himself/herself as a professional; interest and inclination to the occupation (Derkach, 1993; Kuzmina, 1990); the system of the motives of the occupation advantages (Bozhovych, 1972; Leontyev, 1977); personal orientation at the employment of the knowledge, experience, skills in the field of the chosen vocation (Dyachenko & Kandybovych, 1976); the specific type of the values; settings for the given type of activity or as a complex of the several enumerated features (Mytyna, 2003; Zeyer, 2006).

Summing up the findings of the theoretical analysis of the literary sources, professional orientation is understood as mental preparedness of a personality for the chosen occupation, revealed in the cognitive interest, needs, values, persuasions, world outlook, professional inclinations and views.

In literature on psychology there are certain discrepancies as to the structural components of professional orientation, because it comprises two aspects: firstly, these are the peculiarities of the personality orientation; secondly – characteristic, connected with vocation and occupation. The professional orientation has been in the focus of the research of many scholars, most of which considered motivational tendencies its central component (Kostuk, 1977; Lomov, 1984), but quite a number of psychologists didn't limit the definition of the professional orientation components by the boundaries of the system of impulses (Andreyeva, 2004; Gubayidullina, 2000 etc).

On the basis of the findings of the conducted theoretical analysis of the scientific sources, professional orientation structure is viewed as the combination of the three components: motivating-focusing, represented by the vector «motive – objective»; emotive-gnostic, represented by sensual-informational products; regulatory, formed by the volitional and estimating components.

Depending on the degree of the correspondence between the dominating motive, the advantages of the occupation and its sense there are traditionally differentiated three levels of professional orientation: high, average and low. In case, professional orientation is absent or is only on the initial stage of its formation, its non-formation is diagnosed. Regarding the tree-component structure of the professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, it's worth remarking that all the components of the future psychologists' professional orientation may be on the different levels of formation.

Mental correctional support is of great importance in the system of psychological assistance to the children with impaired mental and physical development, especially in the conditions of the transition of modern special education to integrated and inclusive teaching of people with impaired mental and physical development. The efficiency of the mental correctional support will depend on the mental readiness of future psychologists for professional interaction with the above mentioned category of people. The direct tasks of the mental correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development. is first and foremost their psychological and social adaptation. No less important is also psychological support of the families with such children, especially on the stage of integrating a child with impaired mental and physical development by means of inclusion into the environment of peers with normal level of development.

When providing correctional support to the children with impaired mental and physical development the stimulating function of the professional orientation is distinctly actualized. It contributes to the professional-personal tenacity irrespective of the influence of the outer factors. The crucial role in training psychologists for the work with such category of children is also taken into consideration.

Materials & methods

In the conditions of the state system of special education reformation and transfer from institutionalization to integration practical and personal unpreparedness of postgraduates for the due mental correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development is vividly revealed. There arises the issue of special vocational training, formation and development of certain professionally oriented personal features, providing full-value of mental correctional support, clearly admitting the necessity of the qualified correctional support while including the children with impaired mental and physical development into the environment of peers with normal level of development.

The data, obtained by means of theoretical analysis of the scientific sources on issues of personality's professional orientation, specificity of psychological assistance to the children with impaired mental and physical development, as well as the findings of the empirical study of the psychological peculiarities of the professional orientation on the mental correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development and mechanism of its formation in future psychologists have proved the necessity of the targeted influence upon the process of future professionals training, starting from their first academic year. The development of the future psychologists' professional orientation at mental correctional support of children with impaired mental and physical development as the crucial component of future professionals preparedness for vocational activity is predetermined by the following conditions: 1) the entity of the theoretical and practical approaches in teaching medical and psychological disciplines, displayed in the balance of the theoretical and technological components of future special psychologists' vocational training; 2) the optimization of the process, content, forms and techniques of vocational training; 3) the introduction of the psychological coordination of future special psychologists into the educational process, comprising the worked-out system of training activities for the students of 1-4 years, by modeling the structure, content and technology of the professional activity of providing mental correctional support to the children with impaired

mental and physical development; 4) the activation of the students' practical activity, which consists in the realization of the professional knowledge and skills as well as the personality's potential.

The understanding of the professional orientation as the personality's mental preparedness for the chosen professional activity, revealed in the cognitive interest, needs, values, persuasions, world outlook, professional settings and views, has determined the main goals of the strategy of future special psychologists' professional orientation formation psychological provision: 1) to assist students in specifying, enriching and actualizing the views of professional activity and vocational professional and personal features in the field of special psychology; 2) to contribute to the acquisition by students of their professional settings and aspirations; 3) to help future special psychologists discern the factors of their preparedness for the chosen professional activity, that is to reveal the professionally relevant features, challenging development zones and potential opportunities.

To develop future special psychologists' professional orientation at mental correctional support of children there has been worked out the program of the psychological provision of future special psychologists' formation process on all the stages of students' education in a higher institution. The program is based upon the characteristic of special psychologists' professional activity and on the outlined stages of the professional orientation at mental correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development (Fig. 1).

From the point of psychological and pedagogical approach this program may be considered personally oriented, as it presupposes the tandem of the experienced specialist with a group of students as well as with each student separately to ensure the experience acquisition.

Fig. 1. *The scheme of the psychological influence upon the development of professional orientation at correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development*

Source: Authors' own conception

The program is based upon the individual-creative approach, oriented at the transformation of the conscience and self-conscience of a future specialist, as well as at the reformation of his/her values, persuasions, ideals, which would contribute to self-realization and self-actualization of a future special psychologist's personality, as well as the development of his/her creativity, reflection, individual activity style etc.

The worked-out program of psychological support of the process of the formation of future psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development consists of the following main activity directions.

Psychological diagnostic activity: 1) to diagnose students' individual psychological and personal professional peculiarities; 2) to study personality's professional orientation, to understand the current development level of the motivational field, settings, values, personal students' professional orientation development model; 3) to perform psychological testing aimed at efficient employment of the personality's inner potential; 4) to have an interview on the basis of the testing results, to discuss the results, to draw conclusions based on the results; 5) to perform additional psychological testing in case of unfavorable prognosis.

Consulting activity: 1) to work out recommendations on the basis of the results of psychological diagnostic testing; 2) to give a professional consultation on the basis of the findings of the psychological diagnostic research aimed at improving the level of the personality's professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, efficient employment of the personality's potential; 3) to give individual consultation on the basis of applications, to work out individual models of future psychologists' professional orientation development.

Educating-correctional activity: 1) to provide psychological training to lower the level of alarm, relieve excessive nervous and psychic tension, to correct negative mental states; 2) to work out individual mental correctional program on the basis of students' applications; 3) to arrange events contributing to the acquisition of professional identity, to teach students self-control, self-regulation, self-development, self-realization (training, business games, round tables etc).

Informative-orientation activity: 1) to work out and distribute events aimed at creating the favorable social psychological and creative atmosphere in an academic group, at the department, at the institution on the whole; 2) to arrange events (conferences, workshops etc) which allow to outline the challenges in the field of special psychology and correctional-rehabilitation

support of the children with impaired mental and physical development; 3) cooperation with the student government bodies in arranging meetings with specialists from educational and rehabilitation institutions, which will contribute to the acquisition of experience and the full scope of information about future professional activity of mental correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, its perspectives, formation of adequate perception of the future professional tasks etc.

According to the form of organization the following program is a professional psychological training of the personality development and stimulation of the professional orientation at mental correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development. This strategy has been chosen as it simultaneously contributes to the personality's self-conscience development, value system comprehension, motivation amplification, professionally relevant features improvement and conduct peculiarities formation, the most prominent being the ability to efficiently deal with other people and set solid interpersonal relationship.

The program structure presupposes the combination of theoretical informational knowledge and gaming tasks with further psychological analysis and interpretation, in which professional and psychological orientation is relevant, due to which fact the forecast changes in the personality may be predicted (quantitative, qualitative, structural) and the essential activity components may be transformed into the corresponding personality traits.

The intersystem interrelation between the motivation-targeted, emotive-gnostic and regulatory professional orientation components result in singling out the determinants, which allow to characterize the specificity of its formation. The motivation-targeted component is represented by the dominant motives of occupation selection and mastering, their reliability; the humanistic orientation formation; essential personality orientations and the existence of the personal vocational plan.

The emotive-gnostic component of future specialists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development is determined by the views about the future professional activity, its requirements for a specialist's personality; attitude to the future occupation, the process of mastering it; the presence of professional identification; ability for empathy, tolerance, altruism, attraction; professional reflection.

The regulatory component of future specialists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development preconditions professional self-assessment

formation and development; professional self-preservation; professional prediction and anticipation, as well as the mechanism of facilitation and responsibility for the results of the professional activity.

The specific methodology has been worked out to investigate the above-mentioned determinants. Thus, to define the level of professional orientation at the moment of entering a higher educational institution there has been elaborated the methodology, comprising two tests, an interview and the techniques of studying professional identity statuses (Azbel, 2005). When researching the motivation-targeted future specialists' professional orientation component, the following methodology has been employed: test-questionnaire «The Educational Activity Motivation» (Ilyina, 2006) in order to study the key motives of vocational educating activity; test-questionnaire to investigate motivation-meaningful products of students' personality (Orlov, 1981); as well as the technique of activity results analysis – essay «Why I have chosen the occupation of a special psychologist» to define the motives of special psychologist occupation choice.

The emotive-gnostic component of professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development has been studied by means of the following techniques: the test of color oppositions (Bazhyn & Etkind, 1985) to define future special psychologists' emotional attitude to the chosen professional activity, to the children with impaired mental and physical development, to themselves as special psychologists; techniques of communicative setting diagnostics aimed at defining the level of average communicative tolerance, enabling to follow the tendencies of personality formation on the whole, conditioned by the experience, settings, temperament, morality, mental health; modified test-questionnaire to study empathic tendencies (Mekhrabian, 2002), as well as the author's complex questionnaire «My future occupation», aimed at defining the formation level of the views of special psychologists' future occupation, acquaintance with the tasks of the tasks of the professional activity in this field, professionalism criteria, urgent and forecast challenges of the future occupations, as well as the degree of the satisfaction with the chosen vocation and the aspiration for professional self-improvement in the field of special psychology.

To study the determinants of the regulatory component of the professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development the following techniques have been chosen: the technique of professional self-assessment study by means of ranging, the technique of the multifactor personality research (16PF – P. Kettell's) to achieve professionally relevant individual and psychological

peculiarities of the personality, connected with the professional activity regulation; the analysis of the activity products by means of content-analysis (essay «My professional plans») aimed at defining the preparedness for professional forecasting.

The experimental research was done on the basis of the Institute of the correctional pedagogy and psychology at the National Pedagogical Dragomanov University. The research was carried out in 2015 – 2020 years. The sampling of the experiment participants was represented by 200 people (students I-IV years of the specialties «Psychology (special)», «Speech therapy and practical (special) psychology», « Deaf-and-dumb pedagogy and practical (special) psychology», «Typhlopedagogy and practical (special) psychology»).

On the first stage (2015-2016 years) scientific literature on this topic was studied and analyzed; object, subject, objective and tasks were formulated; the framework was worked out and the techniques were defined, ascertaining experiment was carried out to study the issue at the Institute of the correctional pedagogy and psychology and outline the directions of the further research.

On the second stage (2016-2018 years) there was performed quantitative and qualitative analysis of the ascertaining experiment findings, on this basis the framework of the research and the procedure of the forming experiment was worked out; the program of professional orientation development in the students of the specialty «Psychology (special)» was approved.

The third stage (2018-2020 years) was dedicated to the further realization of the program of psychological support of the development of future special psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, analysis and summing up of the experimental activity findings; the formulation of the general conclusions.

Results

On the basis of the findings it has been concluded that about 48% of the enrollees at the moment of their admission to higher educational institutions on the specialty «Psychology (special)» are not oriented at the work with the children with impaired mental and physical development. This indicates insufficient awareness of the peculiarities of the chosen professional activity, the lack of psychological preparedness for interrelation with this category of people and unwillingness to work with them in the

future. Thus one of the tasks was to increase the level of future special psychologists' professional orientation.

The prevailing in the structure of future special psychologists' professional orientation is motivation not to provide psychological support to the children with impaired mental and physical development, but to assist self-development in the boundaries of psychological occupation and higher education acquisition. It has been found out that the psychological occupation choice was predominantly motivated by cognitive interests in 55% students, in 19% future special psychologists it was motivated by utility. At the same time 15% young people have chosen special psychology field due to the social meaningfulness of the future occupation, 7% students have relied on the background of the respectable adults or due to the personal relationship with the people with impaired mental and physical development; while 4% of the experiment participants regard future occupation to be a possible solution of many personal challenges. The findings reveal the urgency of the issue of special psychology specialists' professional preparation and efficiency of their activity in the future, aimed at psychological correctional support of the people with impaired mental and physical development, as well as proved I-centrism in the activity.

The system of future special psychologists' views on the peculiarities of the chosen professional activity, as well as on the professionally relevant features in the field of special psychology is mostly under-formed or subjective due to a group of factors, in particular: the stereotypical image of a psychologist which was formed both on the basis of the personal background and due to the data from mass media; unawareness of the specific peculiarities of the professional activity as well as vocational requirements etc. On the average only 20% students-psychologists at the Institute of correctional pedagogy and psychology (hereinafter – ICPP) 2d year and 40% future special psychologists 3d year have proved the required level of the formation of the views on the special psychologists' professional activity peculiarities. It should be remarked that in the process of training these professional views become more objective, there occurs slight differentiation between the professional activity of practical and special psychologists, however the majority of senior courses students (about 40%) face challenges connected with tasks formulation and future professional activity problems in psychological support provision, which fact proves the lack of professional identification.

The part of students-psychologists ICPP are not satisfied with the chosen occupation (for 2d year that indicator reached 23%, while already 34% 4th year future professionals denied the possibility of the repeated choice of

special psychologist occupation), approximately one quarter of students 2d-4th years have unidentified attitude to the chosen professional activity. The research have revealed in the majority of students-special psychologists the absence of distinct professional plans, concerning psychological support to the children with impaired mental and physical development, as well as inadequate (approximately in 50% heightened and in 25% lowered) professional self-esteem of oneself as a special psychologist. It's worth noting that future special psychologists at the ICPP face the critical moment in their professional formation in their third year, when due to the increased dissatisfaction or unidentified attitude to the future professional activity there arises the risk of the decrease in professional interests, professional intentions, increase in anxiety level and uncertainty etc.

At the end of vocational training in higher educational institutions only one fifth of students-special psychologists is professionally oriented at psychological support of the people with impaired mental and physical development.

The high level of the formation of professional orientation at correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, which presupposes distinct humanistic orientation, formed professional motives of the social value of professional activity; well-developed altruistic tendencies, ability for empathy in its active form (sympathy), high level of communicative tolerance, real optimism; adequate professional self-assessment, formed on the basis of the formed objective occupation and psychologists' personality images; high level of self-control and self-regulation, which is displayed in the increased stress resistance and responsibility for the professional activity. This was revealed only in 7% of the first year students, 21% of the second year students, 19% of future special psychologists of the third course and 28% of the fourth year students at the ICPP.

The average level of formation of professional orientation at the psychological support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, distinguished by the focus on the sphere of interpersonal relations, cognitive professional motives predominance; presence of altruistic tendencies, ability for empathy in the form of sympathy, the satisfactory level of communicative tolerance, heightened or lowered professional self-esteem, formed on the basis of the simplified occupation and psychologists images; the required level of stress resistance and the unidentified attitude to the professional future, was displayed by 45% future special psychologists of 1st year; 51% students of 2nd year; 49% students-special psychologists of 3d year and 63% of 4th year.

The low level of the formation of professional orientation at correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, revealed in the predominance of the utilitarian professional motives, presence of I-centrism, low level of the ability for empathy, lowered communicative tolerance; lack of formation of professional orientation due to false or slight views of images of occupation and specialists' personality; inclination to frustration tendencies and absence of the willing for self-realization in the chosen vocational field, was revealed in 48% 1st year students at the ICPP, in 28% 2nd year future special psychologists, in 32% young people in 3d year and 9% students-special psychologists in 4th year.

There are three stages in the dynamics of the development of professional orientation at correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development in the educational process: adaptive, locally professional and systematically professional.

The obtained results evidenced that future special psychologists' professional orientation at the adaptive stage of its development (1st year – first term of 2d year) is characterized by certain lack of formation of emotive-gnostic component, revealed in the low competence of the chosen professional activity, the requirements of the future occupation; underdeveloped professionally relevant features; lack of psychological preparedness for the interaction with the children with impaired mental and physical development.

At the locally professional stage (second term of 2d year – 3d year) in the process of their practical interaction with the children with impaired mental and physical development future special psychologists face challenges of option and introduction of theoretical knowledge into practical activity, resulting in the lowered self-assurance as to their potential, fear of interaction with such children. In the centre of the attention there is first and foremost the regulatory component of students' professional orientation. Future special psychologists should be assisted in mastering professional inclinations, becoming aware of possible obstacles of professional development and factors of successful professional activity of providing correctional support to the children with impaired mental and physical development.

On the systematically professional stage (from 4th year up to the vocational training graduation) there arise challenges in regard to the development of the motivating-evaluating component of the 4th year future psychologists' professional orientation. The latter results in contributing to students' awareness of their professional identification, its interrelation with the peculiarities of professional orientation at the correctional support of the

children with impaired mental and physical development; assisting senior students in their choice of the specific field of psychological activity, as well as forecasting individual direction of professional development.

The analysis of the findings has proved the urgency of the introduction into the educational process of the psychological support system focused at the peculiarities of each development stage of the future special psychologists', professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, aimed at stimulating the development of professional preparedness for psychological correctional support of the people with impaired mental and physical development and in-time prevention of the professional deformation to avoid inefficient psychological activity of future professionals in the field of special psychology.

As a result of the activity on the development of the professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development there has been reasonably increased the level of such important determinants as professional views about the specialist psychologists' activity peculiarities and requirements for the personality; objective professional self-assessment of one's abilities as special psychologist; professional identity with the subjects of the future professional activity as well as ability for empathy and tolerance to the children with impaired mental and physical development (Table1).

Table 1. *The Dynamics of the Determinants of the Future Special Psychologists' Professional Orientation at the Correctional Support of the Children with Impaired Mental and Physical Development in the Process of the Psychological Assistance Program Realization*

Source: Authors' own conception

Determinants of PO		Professional Views			Professional Self-assessment			Empathy, Tolerance		
		%	t-criterion	Relevance Level	%	t-criterion	Relevance Level	%	t-criterion	Relevance Level
1st year	before	11	- 7,25	0,000**	10	- 2,60	0,010*	46	8,69	0,000**
	after	25		* p≤0,001			24			* p≤0,05
2nd year	before	28	- 8,66	0,000**	18	- 2,04	0,047*	49	14,78	0,000**
	after	48		** p≤0,001			29			* p≤0,05
3d year	before	46	- 7,67	0,000**	21	- 2,37	0,023*	52	2,43	0,020*
	after	64		** p≤0,001			37			* p≤0,05
4th year	before	67	- 2,30	0,032*	41	- 2,19	0,041*	67	10,3	0,000**
	after	79		* p≤0,05			59			* p≤0,05

Orientation at the findings of the employed techniques and methodology, which have proved statistically deviant, as well as on the criterion of the students' satisfaction from the participation in the program, increase in the efficiency of the practical activity and students' interest both to the knowledge and future professional activity of the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, made it possible to consider the program approbation results positive.

Discussion

The scientific novelty of the findings lies in the fact that:

– *for the first time* the future special psychologist's professional orientation problem has been researched; psychological peculiarities of the future special psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development have been outlined and justified;

– *theoretical grounding* for the complex program of psycho-diagnostics of the professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development of enrollees and future special psychologists has been supplied;

– *the development* of the program with the well-defined contents, devices and techniques of psychological support of the evolution of the psychological orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development on all the stages of their education at higher educational institutions.

The relevance of the findings lies in the development of the complex program of psycho-diagnostics of the professional orientation of enrollees at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, its implementation and employment as a basis for professional orientation support due to improve their personal and professional self-identification; in working out methodological recommendations as to the psychological support of the evolution of the psychological orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development; in the arrangement of enlightening and consultative assistance of students in self-identification and self-development of the complex of professionally relevant features in the process of education.

The developed complex program of psycho-diagnostics will result in the qualitative improvement of the professional selection of enrollees for

education on condition of its employment by admissions boards in higher educational institutions and lecturers in teaching.

Methodological recommendation concerning psychological support of the evolution of the psychological support of the future psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development may be employed by curators of academic groups, practice leaders and scientific consultants (aimed at professional orientation enlightenment).

The perspective of the research is seen in the further study of the efficiency of psychological correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development in the field of professional activity of professionals-special psychologists, participating in social-psychological personal growth training while studying in higher educational institutions.

Conclusions

The theoretical basis outline of the personality's professional orientation and the qualitative analysis of the findings of the carried out empirical research of the psychological peculiarities of the future psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development have allowed to draw the following conclusions:

Personality's orientation is a basic and multisided structure of the personality, preconditioning its individuality and uniqueness; it is a source of activity; it unites the inner psychological conditions determining human social activity, and it is inseparable from the participation in social processes. Professional orientation is studied as a system concept, the manifestation of the common personality's orientation in the activity.

Professional orientation is understood as personality's psychological preparedness for the chosen professional activity, revealed in the cognitive interest, values, convictions, world outlook, professional inclinations and views. Professional orientation structure is represented as the combination of the motivating - targeted; emotive - gnostic and regulatory components.

In regards to the degree of the correspondence of the dominant motive of occupation attractiveness to its objective content there are distinguished three levels of formation: high, average and low. Considering the three components of the structure of professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development, it's worth noting that all the components of future

psychologists' professional orientation may also be on different levels of formation.

It has been concluded that the psychological peculiarities of future special psychologists' professional orientation, characterizing high level of its formation, are distinct humane orientation, formed professional motives of the social benefit of the activity; well-developed altruistic tendencies, ability for empathy in its active form (sympathy), high level of communicative tolerance, real optimism; adequate professional self-assessment, formed on the basis of the existing objective occupation and specialists personality image; high level of self-control and self-regulation, revealed in increased stress resistance and responsibility for professional activity. In the course of the research the high formation level of the professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development has been evidenced in 7% first-year students, 21% second-year students, 19% future special psychologists at the 3d course and 28% fourth-year students at the ICPP.

In the dynamic development of future special psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development in the educational process at the higher educational institution there have been distinguished three stages: adaptive, locally professional and systematically professional, on each stage there arise certain challenges. On the adaptive stage of development future special psychologists' professional orientation is characterized by certain lack of formation of the emotive-gnostic component (there is evidenced low awareness of the peculiarities of the chosen occupation; insufficiently developed professionally relevant features; absence of psychological preparedness for interaction with children with impaired mental and physical development). On the locally professional stage there are faced challenges as to the students' professional orientation regulatory component formation (ill-formed ability to select and transmit theoretical knowledge into practical activity provokes lowered confidence in one's potential, fear of communicating with children etc). On the systematically professional stage there arise problems of the development of motivating-targeted component of future psychologists' professional orientation (incomplete competence of professional identification, its inconsistency with the characteristics of the professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development; absence of the ability to predict individual trajectory of professional development etc).

To raise the level of the future specialists' professional orientation in the field of special psychology at the correctional support of the children

with impaired mental and physical development there has been worked out and grounded the program of the psychological support of the process of students-psychologists' professional orientation formation on all the stages of education at the higher institution. According to the form of organization this program is a social psychological personal growth training of special psychologists, consisting of four modules, each characterized by the clearly defined objective and compliance with the stages of future psychologists' professional orientation at the correctional support of the children with impaired mental and physical development.

On the basis of the obtained findings it may be concluded, that the initial methodology is correct, the set tasks have been fulfilled, the objective has been achieved, the efficiency of the suggested methodological recommendations have been proved.

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